

WETTING BEHAVIOUR OF MOLTEN THERMOPLASTICS: EFFECT OF PHYSICAL AND CHEMICAL INTERACTIONS ON THE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF GLASS FIBRE-THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITE INTERFACES

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ABSTRACT

Direct contact angle measurements were performed between different molten thermoplastics, polypropylene (PP), polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF), and maleic anhydride-grafted polypropylene (MAPP) with different maleic anhydride content, on smooth glass fibres and smooth glass plates. The matrices were selected as model systems for the investigation of the fibre–matrix interface, based on the difference in surface energies between PP and PVDF (physical interactions) and the effect of chemical bonding between PP and MAPP. In this way, physical and chemical adhesion were studied independently. The mechanical strength of the interfaces was then assessed by single fibre pull-out tests. The interfacial strength and the wettability of molten thermoplastics correspond well to the predictions based on the calculation of the theoretical work of adhesion between the matrices and the fibre surfaces for PP and PVDF; however, the wetting behaviour of molten MAPP is affected by the MA content if compared with the surface energy analysis made at room temperature. The hypothesis is that the ring opening of the maleic anhydride group at high temperature leads to a strong increase in polarity of the polymer and thus to a lower contact angle with the glass surface.

1 INTRODUCTION

The interaction between the reinforcing fibre and the matrix has a significant effect on the properties of the composite since the load distribution efficiency at the interface is determined by the degree of adhesion between the components. This strong fibre-matrix adhesion has to be obtained by interfacial interactions, including mechanical interlocking, chemical bonding and physical mechanisms of adhesion [1].

Mechanical interlocking can have two opposing effects: promote or decrease adhesion. If the matrix is not able to fill irregularities at the fibre surface, the area of contact between the fibre and the matrix will be reduced, producing in turn a reduction in adhesion; on the other hand if the matrix can fully wet the rough surface, mechanical interlocking and increased contact area will lead to increased adhesion. Chemical adhesion will also depend on the degree of wetting, and it is formed across the interface if atoms of the fibre surface molecules can share electrons with matrix atoms, producing a very high bond strength.

The molecules at the fibre surface are also able to interact with one another and with molecules from the matrix, without undergoing covalent bonding. The common procedure to evaluate these physical interactions is to estimate the composition of the fibre surface and the matrix in terms of surface energy components, utilising the results of contact angle measurements of probe liquids on both the fibre and

the matrix in solid state at room temperature [2]. However, there is a lack of information on how the interface is formed at high temperature between the molten thermoplastic and the hot fibre surface, and how high temperature affects the wetting behaviour of molten polymers during composite manufacturing.

The aim of this paper is to study the influence of physical adhesion on the mechanical behaviour of interfaces between a glass fibre and PP, MAPP, and PVDF matrices. Physical adhesion was experimentally determined by measuring contact angles with different probe liquids using the Wilhelmy technique and by applying the acid-base theory for calculating the surface energy components and the wetting parameters. These values were compared to those obtained by direct contact angle measurements of the molten thermoplastics on glass. The mechanical strength of the interfaces/interphases was characterized by the critical local value of interfacial shear stress, τ_d , at the moment of crack initiation, obtained by single fibre pull-out tests, and then used for correlating thermodynamic work of adhesion and practical adhesion.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Materials

The silica core (diameter: 200 μm) of optical glass fibres from Thorlabs (FR200UMT) were used in this study. Polypropylene (PP), maleic anhydride-grafted polypropylene (MAPP, Bynel 50E725), and polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF, Solef 1008) were obtained from Propex, Dupont, and Solvay respectively.

2.2 Materials preparation

Only the silica core of the optical glass fibres is needed, and thus the outer layers have to be removed. The cladding layer is removed by submerging the stripped fibres in hot sulphuric acid. The fibres were submerged in piranha solution (mixture of concentrated sulphuric acid and hydrogen peroxide) for 30 minutes. Finally, the glass fibres were rinsed off with water and stored in ultrapure water (resistivity > 18M Ω .cm) for avoiding environmental organic contamination.

For contact angle measurement of the molten polymer on glass, a flat glass surface was obtained by melting the silica core.

2.3 Contact angle measurements and surface energy analysis

Advancing and receding contact angles of various test liquids (ultrapure water: 18.2 Ω cm resistivity, diiodomethane: Merck, and ethylene glycol: Sigma–Aldrich) were measured on the polymer films and glass fibres under controlled conditions (temperature of 20°C and humidity of 50%), with a Krüss K100 tensiometer using the Wilhelmy technique [3, 4]. In order to better describe both the low surface energy and the high surface energy components of the analysed surfaces, the average of the cosines of the advancing (θ_{adv}) and receding (θ_{rec}) angles was used for the glass fibres to estimate the cosine of the equilibrium angle (θ_{equ}), as has been suggested by Andrieu et al.[5], and is shown in Equation 1.

$$\cos \theta_{equ} = 0.5 \cos \theta_{adv} + 0.5 \cos \theta_{rec} \quad (1)$$

Surface energy components were calculated according to the Van Oss model and by using the SurfTen 4.3 software developed by Claudio Della Volpe [6]. Also, the work of adhesion (W_a), the spreading coefficient (S), the wetting tension (ΔF), and the interfacial energy (γ_{sl}), which are wetting parameters related to the interfacial strength [7], are calculated according to the following equations:

$$W_a = \gamma_s + \gamma_l - \gamma_{sl} = \gamma_l (1 + \cos \theta_{equ}) \quad (2)$$

$$S = \gamma_s - (\gamma_l + \gamma_{sl}) \quad (3)$$

$$\Delta F = \gamma_s - \gamma_{sl} = \gamma_l \cos \theta_{equ} \quad (4)$$

$$\gamma_{sl} = \left(\sqrt{\gamma_s^{LW}} - \sqrt{\gamma_l^{LW}} \right)^2 + 2 (\sqrt{\gamma_s^+} - \sqrt{\gamma_l^+}) (\sqrt{\gamma_s^-} - \sqrt{\gamma_l^-}) \quad (5)$$

Where $\gamma_{s,l}$ represents the surface energy (solid and liquid respectively), γ_s^{LW} represents the Lifshitz-van der Waals component, $\gamma_{s,l}^+$ represents the acidic, and $\gamma_{s,l}^-$ the basic component.

The polymers are molten in a chamber with controlled inert gas environment to avoid degradation at 200°C. For measuring the contact angle of a molten polymer on a fibre, the latter is gradually introduced into a liquid polymer until the meniscus is formed, and then its contour shape is fitted with the Young-Laplace equation to calculate the contact angle.

For analysing the wetting behaviour of the molten thermoplastic on a flat surface, a droplet is formed with the liquid thermoplastic and the contour shape is also fitted with the Young-Laplace equation.

2.4 Pull-out test

A block of polymer was put in an aluminium cylindrical container with a radius of 5 mm and heated until the melting temperature. When the polymer was completely molten, the fibre was placed perpendicularly to the polymer surface and in it was centred with the help of an optical microscope to guarantee accuracy.

The evaluation of the interfacial debonding strength, τ_d , and the interfacial friction, τ_f , was made by following the procedure developed by Zhandarov et al. [8, 9], and the methodology can be consulted in our previous publication [1].

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 shows the advancing, receding, and equilibrium contact angles. The latter were used for the calculation of the surface energy components of the thermoplastic surfaces, which are shown in Table 2. As expected, PVDF possesses higher acidity due to the different electro-negativities of carbon, fluorine, and hydrogen. In particular, the strong inductive effect of the fluorine atoms polarizes the electronic distribution of partially fluorinated polymers [10].

For the case of PP, we find a deviation in the magnitude of the polar surface energy component, which was expected to be zero since pure PP is a nonpolar polymer. This effect could be related to aging processes or surface contamination [11]. For the case of MAPP, the determined surface energy shows an increment of polar components possibly due to the presence of maleic anhydride [11].

liquid	PP			MAPP			PVDF		
	adv	rec	equ	adv	rec	equ	adv	rec	equ
WT	97.8 ±1.6	74.1 ±1.5	86.0 ±1.1	99.7 ±1.3	64.2 ±0.9	82.3 ±0.8	85.5 ±0.9	68.9 ±1.2	77.3 ±0.7
EG	71.1 ±0.6	49.4 ±1.7	60.8 ±0.8	84.8 ±1.3	41.7 ±0.8	65.3 ±0.8	54.1 ±1.2	32.1 ±1.6	44.2 ±0.9
DIO	67.9 ±1.2	46.1 ±1.7	57.7 ±1.0	77.9 ±0.9	38.1 ±0.5	60.1 ±0.5	63.6 ±0.4	46.5 ±1.8	55.5 ±0.8

Table 1: Advancing, receding and equilibrium contact angles of probe liquids on thermoplastic surfaces: water (WT), ethylene glycol (EG), diodomethane (DIO).

Material	γ^{tot} (mJ/m ²)	γ^{LW} (mJ/m ²)	γ^{ab} (mJ/m ²)	γ^+ (mJ/m ²)	γ^- (mJ/m ²)
Glass	40.5 ± 2.1	29.7 ± 0.2	10.9 ± 0.2	1.1 ± 0.2	27.3 ± 0.1
PP	30.9 ± 0.5	29.9 ± 0.5	1.0 ± 0.2	0.1 ± 0.0	2.0 ± 0.3
MAPP	29.1 ± 0.4	28.5 ± 0.3	0.6 ± 0.2	0.0 ± 0.0	3.7 ± 0.3
PVDF	34.6 ± 0.5	31.2 ± 0.5	3.5 ± 0.2	0.9 ± 0.1	3.3 ± 0.2

Table 2: Surface energy components of glass fibre and thermoplastic films.

The work of adhesion, spreading coefficient, wetting tension, and interfacial energy for glass fibre as substrate were calculated for the various polymers by using equations 2,3,4 and 5 respectively (see Table 3).

Material	W_a (mJ/m ²)	S (mJ/m ²)	γ_{sl} (mJ/m ²)	ΔF (mJ/m ²)
PP	66.00 ± 0.99	4.26 ± 0.99	5.37 ± 0.35	35.13 ± 1.30
MAPP	62.66 ± 0.65	4.46 ± 0.65	6.94 ± 0.13	33.56 ± 0.25
PVDF	70.76 ± 0.76	1.48 ± 0.76	4.38 ± 0.28	36.12 ± 0.36

Table 3: Wetting parameters with glass fibre as the substrate.

The results for PP and MAPP present a relatively low W_a and ΔF (if compared with PVDF) due to their almost zero polar component. It has to be noted that these values are only related to intramolecular physical forces and do not relate to covalent bonding (which is important in the case of MAPP).

On the other hand, PVDF shows a higher W_a than PP and MAPP, as well as a positive S value and a low γ_{sl} , helping to achieve a good wetting of the molten polymer on the glass fibre. Furthermore, the ΔF value is the highest corresponding to the situation where W_a is maximum within the region where spontaneous wetting occurs [12]. This strong interfacial interaction is a consequence of electron donor-acceptor interactions due to the presence of a relatively high acidic component in PVDF and a high basic component on the glass fibre's surface; as well as a relatively high total surface energy of both the matrix and the substrate. Since polar interactions are electron donor-acceptor interactions, strong interfacial interactions occur only when one phase has basic and the other has acidic sites.

There was a good correlation between the interfacial parameters determined from the pull-out test and the theoretical W_a for glass as substrate. As it can be seen in Table 4, the value of τ_d for the PVDF-glass fibre system is approximately 5 times higher than the values obtained for the PP-glass system. The latter clearly indicates a higher interfacial adhesion and greater surface energy components compatibility of PVDF on glass fibres if compared with the PP system.

Matrix	τ_d (MPa)	τ_f (MPa)	W_a (mJ/m ²)
PP	7.9	2.9	66.0
MAPP	17.0	1.6	62.7
PVDF	37.0	1.4	70.8

Table 4: Interfacial parameters determined from the pull-out test. W_a from Table 3.

If the PVDF and PP glass fibre systems are compared, the obtained τ_f value for the PVDF is lower in case of PP (see Table 4). Even though the roughness of the fibres was the same for the 2 glass systems, the effect of friction is apparently lower for PVDF than for the PP system. This may be related to the difficulty of PVDF to spread on the glass surface due to its low spreading coefficient (see Table 3), reducing the amount of area in contact with the glass surface and also reducing the mechanical interlocking, as the matrix does not penetrate that well into the surface roughness.

Regarding MAPP, although the W_a is the lowest of the three polymers, the obtained τ_d is considerably higher than for PP. The reason is the chemical bonding formed between the anhydride groups from the polymer and the hydroxyl groups from the glass surface.

The adhesion at the interface of MAPP has improved with respect to PP through chemical bonding (higher τ_d) but the strength of MAPP is even lower than the strength of PP (55 MPa and 30 MPa for PP

and MAPP respectively); therefore, with a stronger interface, the failure occurs in the matrix. This can be observed in the SEM images of already pulled-out fibres, where remnants of MAPP can be observed on the fibre surface (see figure 1). Even though, MAPP is chemically bonded to the glass fibre, the adhesion strength is not better than the one of the PVDF system due to matrix failure.

Figure 1: Pulled-out surfaces at the same magnification of MAPP (left), PP (center), PVDF (right).

In order to compare whether the physical interactions of molten thermoplastics and hot solid surfaces correspond to those utilising the results of contact angle measurements of probe liquids on both the fibre and the matrix in solid state at room temperature, contact angles of molten PVDF, PP and PVDF on glass were measured (see Figure 2). As it can be seen in Table 5, the contact angles correspond well to our previous surface energy analysis for PVDF and PP. As expected the contact angles for PVDF are lower than for PP, due to the better compatibility of PVDF and glass.

Figure 2: Contact angle evolution of molten MAPP on flat glass substrate (left), and the meniscus formation of molten PVDF on a glass fibre (right)

For the case of MAPP, although the total surface energy and their components are very similar to those of PP (see Table 2), its contact angle at 200°C is the lowest, and the explanation might be related to the ring opening of the maleic anhydride group at high temperature, which may lead to a strong increase in polarity of the polymer and thus to a lower contact angle with the glass surface. This will be checked by surface energy component characterization at high temperature. It is also possible that the formation of covalent bonds at the interface may be lowering the contact angle as well. The low contact

angle of MAPP on glass corresponds well with the pull-out results, showing a higher τ_d for the MAPP-glass system even though the Wa at room temperature is lower than for PP (see Table 4).

Matrix	Fibre C.A. (°)	Surface C.A. (°)
PP	37.4 ± 0.9	39.4 ± 1.1
MAPP	19.6 ± 0.4	21.4 ± 1.5
PVDF	32.3 ± 0.5	28.6 ± 1.7

Table 5: Static advancing contact angles of molten PP, MAPP, and PVDF on glass substrate (glass and flat surface) at 200 °C.

9 CONCLUSIONS

Surface interactions and interface compatibility between PP, MAPP, and PVDF with glass substrates were evaluated by three different methods: surface energy calculation by utilising the results of contact angle measurements of probe liquids on both the fibre and the matrix in solid state at room temperature, direct contact angle measurement of molten thermoplastic on glass substrate, and pull-out tests.

The pull-out test results correspond well to the theoretical predictions of adhesion for PP and PVDF, based on surface energy component characterization. For the case of MAPP, its wetting behaviour is affected by the presence of MA groups and at high temperature this leads to the lowest contact angle, even if the surface energy component analysis at room temperature shows no difference with PP. This indicates a good compatibility of MAPP during composite manufacture on top of covalent bond formation.

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